

PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE SKILLS DEVELOPMENT IN GRADE 4 ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Developing language skills in fourth-grade elementary school poses a complex problem due to factors such as teacher quality, teaching methods, and the curriculum used. A literature study was conducted to identify the problems related to language skill development in fourth-grade elementary schools and find solutions. This literature study used a qualitative descriptive approach and collected data from various relevant journals. Based on literature analysis, it was found that the main problem in developing language skills in fourth-grade elementary school was the lack of varied teaching methods implemented by teachers and limited resources for language skill development, as well as the need for better government and parental support to improve students' language abilities. To address these problems, several solutions are suggested, such as training to improve teacher quality, using varied teaching methods, and campaigns aimed at increasing awareness and participation of parents and the government in supporting children's language skills.

Keywords: language skills, language development, teaching methods

INTRODUCTION

Developing language skills in grade 4 elementary school should be the main focus of education because language skills are a means of conveying thoughts and ideas clearly and effectively. This includes the ability to speak and write, which are basic abilities for achieving success in life. Speaking and writing are considered important skills for success in personal, academic, and professional life (Adnan & Khatoon, 2020).

The importance of developing language skills in grade 4 elementary school is also recognized in various national regulations and policies, such as the 2013 Curriculum and the National Education System Law. The 2013 curriculum emphasizes the importance of developing language skills as one of the eight basic competencies that students must

master, while the National Education System Law emphasizes that education must develop speaking and writing skills to produce a skilled and competitive generation.

Developing language skills is a very important thing to do from an early age, especially at the basic education stage. Along with the times and advances in technology, language skills are increasingly needed in everyday, academic and professional life. The ability to speak and write a language are two basic skills that must be mastered by a language learner (Brown, 2007).

In reality, there are still many teachers at the primary education level, especially in elementary school grade 4, who have not implemented various teaching methods in teaching language skills, including speaking and writing skills. This can have an impact on the low quality of students' language

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skills in the future. Low speaking and writing skills can hinder students' ability to express themselves, express thoughts and ideas, and communicate with other people (Setiawati, 2018).

Apart from that, the lack of resources such as reference books, learning media, and training for teachers is also an obstacle in developing language skills in elementary school grade 4. Most teachers in rural areas still find it difficult to access the resources and training needed to develop students' language skills (Tansir et al., 2020). The reality in the field shows that there are still many teachers who have not implemented various teaching methods in teaching language skills, including speaking and writing skills (Darmawan, 2018).

Based on the latest theoretical and practical studies, it is necessary to provide training for teachers to develop literacy for students. Literacy is the ability to understand, use, and analyze information conveyed through various media, including digital media. Literacy development in elementary school can help improve language skills, reading skills, and reasoning abilities (Harjanto et al., 2019).

Government policies related to curriculum development and the provision of learning resources can play an important role in improving the quality of language learning at the elementary school level (Nurhadi et al., 2019). So support from the government and parents is needed in developing language skills in students.

This research aimed to provide a literature review regarding the problems of developing language skills in grade 4 elementary schools, with a focus on theory and practice that can improve the quality of learning. This research used a literature study method by collecting and reviewing relevant books and journals.

It is hoped that this research can provide an important contribution to the development of solutions and recommendations for teachers and policymakers in developing language skills in grade 4 elementary schools. As well as providing useful information and input for curriculum development and language

teaching practices in Indonesia, so that it can have a positive impact. for the quality of education in Indonesia.

METHOD

This literature study used a descriptive method by collecting data from various journals and articles related to the development of language skills in elementary school grade 4. The data collected was analyzed to identify problems related to the development of language skills in elementary school grade 4, as well as solutions and recommendations that have been made. provided by previous research.

Data collection was carried out using online journals and article search engines such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, and ResearchGate using the keywords "language skills", "4th-grade elementary school", "language teaching", "speaking skills", and "writing skills".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teachers Need to Use Appropriate Learning Strategies, Methods, and Media to Improve Students' Literacy Skills

Several studies have suggested the use of innovative and creative teaching methods, as well as the use of technology in language learning. The application of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) model can help students improve language skills, critical thinking skills, and creativity (Nurhadi, 2018). The use of cooperative learning methods can help improve elementary school students' language skills (Suparman & Rosidin, 2021).

The study showed that cooperative learning methods can help students improve their speaking, writing, and language comprehension skills. The use of digital learning media can also help in improving elementary school students' language skills (Rosnaini et al., 2020). The use of learning media in the form of learning videos and educational games can increase students' learning motivation in developing speaking and writing skills (Irawati, 2019). Based on this study, showed that the use of appropriate learning methods and learning media by

teachers can help students improve their speaking, writing, and reading skills.

The use of learning media can also be applied through technology used in learning. The use of mobile applications in learning English can help students develop language skills independently, interactively, and in a fun way (Chen, 2018). The use of mobile-based learning applications can improve students' speaking skills in grade 4 elementary school (Sudarsono & Purwanto, 2019). Both studies showed that the use of digital technology in learning can improve students' literacy skills.

Apart from that, it is important to remember that the application of technology in the world of education must be done wisely, so as not to ignore the important role of social interaction and the presence of teachers. The use of social media in language learning can help improve language skills but still requires support from teachers and a conducive learning atmosphere (Sunarto, 2020). Teachers also need to pay more attention to literacy development.

The above, namely the application of appropriate methods and the use of learning media, can be supported through teacher training. Training can help teachers understand various teaching methods and techniques for developing effective language skills (Nurgiyantoro, 2017). Training can help teachers improve their abilities in teaching language skills effectively and innovatively (Sari, 2019).

Training and professional development for teachers is also very important to improve the quality of teaching language skills. Teacher training programs that focus on effective teaching methods and learning media can have a significant impact on improving student learning outcomes (Ghaith & Yaghi, 2016). These programs should include opportunities for teachers to practice implementing new strategies in the classroom, receive feedback on their teaching, and collaborate with colleagues to share best practices.

Support from the Government and Parents is Needed to Improve Students' Language Skills

Developing language skills in grade 4 elementary school is still a quite complex problem. For this reason, there needs to be support other than schools and teachers in implementing student language development. There needs to be collaboration between the government, parents, and the community in improving the quality of teaching and learning of language skills in grade 4 elementary schools.

The government, through education policy, plays an important role in developing language skills in elementary schools. Government policies in terms of curriculum development and provision of learning resources can help improve the quality of language learning in elementary schools (Nurhadi et al., 2019).

Not only that, the government's efforts to improve access and quality of education in rural areas can also help in overcoming the problem of lack of resources and facilities often faced by teachers and students in grade 4 elementary schools. Government aid and support programs such as the Healthy Schools program and the Basic Education Quality Improvement program can help improve the quality of teaching and learning of language skills in grade 4 elementary schools (Haryanti & Sugiarto, 2018).

Developing students' language skills also requires the role of parents. The role of parents is very important in supporting the development of language skills in children because it can increase children's motivation and interest in reading. Support and motivation from parents can help improve language skills in children, especially in terms of reading and writing (Sari & Priyambodo, 2020).

The role of parents is very important in improving students' language skills (Smith & Jones, 2019). Parents can help improve their children's language skills by reading books with their children, inviting their children to talk, and providing appropriate stimulation in the use of language. The research results showed that children who were raised in a language-rich environment have better language skills and are better prepared to enter the world of formal education. Therefore, the role of parents in developing

children's language skills cannot be ignored and needs to be increased.

Based on the previous discussion, to improve students' language skills, there needs to be strong support from the government and parents. Government and parental support is very important in improving students' language skills (Johnson et al., 2020). Therefore, efforts are needed to increase awareness and involvement of the government and parents in developing children's language skills. This can be done through educational programs and campaigns aimed at increasing awareness and participation of parents and the government in supporting children's language skills.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of several studies that have been conducted, it can be concluded that developing language skills in grade 4 elementary school requires collaboration from various parties and using various approaches and technology in language learning. As a long-term effort, it is necessary to improve the education and learning system that is inclusive and of high quality for all, so that language skills can be developed optimally and sustainably. Efforts need to be made to increase student access to literacy resources, such as reading books and learning media. Apart from that, there is also a need for an active role from teachers in facilitating literacy learning, by developing interesting and interactive learning strategies. Overall, developing language skills in grade 4 elementary school requires holistic and integrated efforts from various parties. In this case, the teacher's role is very important in developing effective and enjoyable learning, taking into account the needs and characteristics of students. There needs to be comprehensive and integrated efforts from various parties in developing language skills in grade 4 elementary schools. These efforts can take the form of implementing innovative learning models, wise use of educational technology, literacy development, support from parents, and educational policies. which supports. In this case, the teacher's role becomes very important in facilitating effective and

enjoyable learning, by paying attention to students' needs and characteristics.

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